

Memoized Derivatives for Fast Filtering and Schema Validation of Semi-Structured Data

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We present a high-performance filtering and schema-validation algorithm based on Brzozowski’s derivatives, extended to regular hedge grammars for semi-structured data. Our algorithm inherits the expressiveness of regular hedge grammars to support a wide range of schema languages and serialization formats, such as JSON Schema, RELAX NG for XML, and Protocol Buffers. High performance is achieved by refactoring the derivative algorithm to make it more amenable to memoization of hedges. We verify in Lean that our memoization technique is correct: our memoized filtering and validation algorithm is equivalent to the denotational semantics of regular hedge grammars. This is the first proof of correctness in an interactive theorem prover of a derivative algorithm for regular hedge grammars or schema languages. We combine the memoization technique with the fusion of the parsing and derivative algorithms to avoid creating intermediate parsing data structures. Benchmarking is done on an implementation in Go against several other JSON Schema implementations. We end up with the fastest library in the filtering use case when considering median latency, providing evidence that derivatives are a competitive approach for validation, even for semi-structured data.

CCS Concepts: • **Software and its engineering** → **Semantics; Software verification**; • **Theory of computation** → **Regular languages**; • **Applied computing** → **Document searching**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: regular hedge grammar, high-performance filtering, schema validation, formal verification, Brzozowski derivative, Lean, JSON Schema, Protocol Buffers.

1 Introduction

Filtering and validating semi-structured data such as Extensible Markup Language (XML), JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), and Protocol Buffers [45] is a recurring task in distributed systems. We present our Katydid¹ filtering algorithm, designed to achieve high performance via a novel memoization technique and a fused algorithm.

Our approach is based on Brzozowski derivatives [5], a classical technique for recognizing regular languages. We adapt this derivative algorithm to operate on regular hedge grammars, which generalize regular expressions to *hedges*, or, informally, to tree-shaped data. These grammars form the foundation of schema languages such as RELAX NG [18] and JSON Schema [37]. They enable expressive constraints over ordered and unordered element sequences, nesting, repetition, and recursion.

We build on derivatives because they offer exactly the properties a high-throughput, verifiable filter needs. The derivative of a regular expression is itself a regular expression (*residuality*), making intermediate states first-class. Memoization is therefore inherent, directly transforming cache hits into state transitions without requiring an explicit automaton. Regular expressions have finitely many derivatives up to similarity [5, 51] and justify a *bounded* memoization table that underlies the lazy Deterministic Finite Automaton (DFA) construction popularized by Owens et al. [36]. Derivatives also handle boolean operators directly, which allows the modeling of JSON Schema’s

¹A Katydid is a leaf insect that camouflages (requires filtering) itself in trees (data structures).

"allOf", "anyOf", "oneOf", and "not" without leaving the framework. Finally, a derivative-based algorithm is easier to verify than a bespoke validator: its structure is a small recursive function over the schema, which we exploit to give a machine-checked correctness proof.

Because our algorithm operates on regular hedge grammars rather than any single schema language, it applies uniformly across schema languages and serialization formats—RELAX NG, JSON Schema, and Protocol Buffers. Our main contribution beyond prior derivative validators is that we build a high-performance *filtering* library, not merely a validator: filtering through large volumes of mostly non-matching records is a use case for which existing JSON Schema validators are not designed, and it is where fusing derivation with parsing pays off. Derivative-based recognition is, moreover, competitive in practice: Moseley et al. [31] built a derivative-based, non-backtracking engine that ships as a regular expression backend in .NET 7, demonstrating that derivatives can be fast on real-world workloads, at least in the string case. We extend this evidence from flat strings to tree-shaped, semi-structured data.

Outside our Katydid algorithm, there are two other derivative-based algorithms for schema validation: RELAX NG [7] and JSONmembers — a term we adopt for the procedure introduced by Holstege [17]. JSONmembers flattens the JSON object into a sequence of members (key-value pairs) and takes the derivative given one member at a time. Holstege [17] explicitly notes that the performance is not compelling, and it is difficult to find a memoization solution because the derivative is taken on an infinite input alphabet.

RELAX NG [7] converts the schema into a Balanced Context Free Grammar (BCFG) on the fly as it applies derivatives. The algorithm decomposes the derivative function into smaller components that can be memoized, exploiting the limited variation in XML element nodes. It implements memoization that only uses the schema and element names in the memoization table. The element names have a large alphabet but low variance, which results in many hits in the memoization table. However, this memoization strategy runs into similar problems because the text nodes have a large and highly variable string alphabet. To address the challenge of this high variability, they only memoize element nodes and not text nodes. Also, the memoization technique is unbounded in the number of entries to be memoized. The table grows with inputs that have new element names or deeper recursion.

We restructure the derivative function to have memoization that is alphabet independent. This refactors the derivative function into a composition of three stages—enter, evaluate predicates, and leave—of which the first and last are memoized and alphabet independent. The big improvement our algorithm makes over RELAX NG is that it can optionally create a fully memoized table before seeing any input, and the number of entries in the table is bounded, see [Section 4.4](#). Our main contributions are: (1) The factorization of the derivative function for regular hedge grammars that enables alphabet independent memoization and bounds the size of the memoization table for performant filtering; (2) The first formal verification of derivative algorithms for regular hedge grammars, proving in Lean [10] that our implementation of the JSONmembers algorithm and Katydid’s memoization technique faithfully match the semantics of a regular hedge grammar; (3) A fused [16] derivative and parsing algorithm that removes the overhead of creating intermediate parsing data structures; (4) Abstraction of serialization formats behind a pull-based parser interface in Go [15] that allows for regular hedge grammar validation of Protocol Buffers, JSON, XML, and reflected Go structures; and (5) A significant extension of the JSON Schema benchmark suite developed by Viotti and Mior [47], which we use to benchmark our Go implementation of Katydid.

The original requirement of this work was schema-based filtering at scale in a proprietary distributed database that stored denormalized Protocol Buffers. To meet production-level performance requirements, we implemented the memoization technique and fused algorithm in Go [15] with a

strong emphasis on avoiding heap allocations. The benchmarks of this implementation demonstrate its ability to filter data at high speeds and that it competes with other JSON Schema validators.

Definitions, proofs, as well as pseudocode for the Go implementation are presented in the syntax of the Lean theorem prover [10] and are available in the [supplementary material](#)². Lean tutorials are available online [27]. To help readers who are less familiar with Lean, we recall some conventions close to where they are used. We deliberately chose to state our definitions and theorems in Lean rather than in parallel mathematical notation. This keeps a single source of truth and avoids duplication: the statements in the paper are exactly the ones checked by the theorem prover, so there is no informal-to-formal transcription gap for the reader to second-guess, and no risk that a hand-written version subtly diverges from what was actually proven. We only use the Lean standard library and standard axioms, and the code is sorry free.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. [Section 3](#) explains the Katydid algorithm. [Section 4](#) presents formal verifications. In [Section 5](#), we describe the Go implementation, which includes the generic pull-based parser, the fused algorithm, and how JSON Schema is supported. We follow up in [Section 6](#) with benchmark results against other JSON Schema implementations. [Section 7](#) covers related work, and [Section 8](#) outlines the directions for future research. In [Section 2](#), we start with a simple JSON Schema example to illustrate and motivate our approach.

2 Motivating Example

The purpose of this section is to demonstrate the Katydid algorithm in a simplified setting. We describe the algorithm in more detail in [Section 3](#) and [Section 5](#).

To illustrate the application of Brzozowski’s derivative algorithm to JSON Schema, we use a simplified schema of a blog post [21]:

```
{ "title": "small jsonschema for a blogpost",
  "type": "object", "additionalProperties": false, "required": ["content"],
  "properties": { "content": { "type":"string" },
    "author": { "$ref":"#/definitions/profile" } },
  "definitions": { "profile": {
    "type": "object", "additionalProperties": false, "required": ["username"],
    "properties": { "username": { "type":"string" },
      "email": { "type":"string", "format":"email" } } } } }
```

The schema requires a content field and an optional author object. The author object must contain a username and may contain an email address. For example: `{"content": "Dragons", "author": {"username": "Khaleesi"}}`.

Brzozowski’s derivative algorithm for regular expressions consumes one input symbol and returns a residual regular expression. The *JSONmembers* algorithm of Holstege [17] is a derivative-based validation algorithm for JSON Schema that adapts this idea from strings to JSON objects. By flattening the JSON object into a list of key-value pairs (members), the input symbols are now key-value pairs, and the derivative of a schema with respect to an input symbol is a residual schema. For this example, we will use the flattened input: `[{"content": "Dragons"}, {"author": {"username": "Khaleesi"}}]`. We first take the derivative of the schema with respect to the first object, `{"content": "Dragons"}`. The only field left in the residual schema is `"author"`:

```
{ "type": "object", "additionalProperties": false,
  "properties": { "author": { "$ref":"#/definitions/profile" } } ... }
```

²No part of the Lean code (including the formal proofs) or the Go code was created with the aid of GenAI (LLMs).

Table 1. The bounded memoization tables for enter and leave

enter table		leave table $\xrightarrow{\quad}$	
key: schema	value: predicate/schema pairs	key (schema, boolean)	value: residual
blogpost	[{"content", ...}, {"author", ...}]	(blogpost, [true, false])	optional "author"
profile	[{"username", ...}, {"email", ...}]	(profile, [true, false])	optional "email"
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

We next take the derivative of this residual schema with respect to the remaining key-value pair `{"author": {"username": "Khaleesi"}}`. The result is an empty schema, `{"type": "object", "additionalProperties": false}`. There are no more key-value pairs to process in the input, and the empty object is valid against the residual schema, so the input is accepted.

Memoization of the derivative can improve performance if later calls reuse memoization keys that have already been stored. For JSONmembers, the memoization key is a pair of the schema and a member (key-value pair). Values such as titles, usernames, timestamps, identifiers, and text fields vary from one input object to the next. Therefore, memoization keys do not get reused, and memoization is not effective. For the first derivative in our example schema, the input objects `{"content": "Dragons"}` and `{"content": "Eggs"}` result in the same residual schema but have different memoization keys. The Katydid algorithm makes memoization effective by factoring the derivative into three stages: enter, predicate evaluation, and leave. The enter function is well suited to memoization because its only argument is the schema. For the first derivative in our example, enter extracts two predicate/schema pairs from the schema:

- the "content" field predicate and `{"type": "string"}` schema; and
- the "author" field predicate and the referenced "profile" schema.

After extracting these predicates, the input object is evaluated against them, and the algorithm is recursively applied to the schemas to produce a boolean Vector. For our example `{"content": "Dragons"}`, the predicate/schema pairs evaluate to: `[true, false]`. The first boolean is true because the field name is "content" and the value "Dragons" is of string type. The second boolean is false because the field name is not "author". The leave function then combines the schema argument with this boolean Vector to compute the residual schema. In our example, the first predicate succeeds, so leave returns the schema in which only the "author" field remains. The leave function is well suited to memoization, since the input object values do not appear in the cache key. When evaluating predicate/schema pairs against the input objects, for example `{"content": "Dragons"}` and `{"content": "Eggs"}` both produce `[true, false]` and so the memoization entry for leave is reused. No input value ever appears in the keys, see Table 1.

The factored derivative function is iteratively applied to the rest of the input to also end up with an empty schema, which matches the empty object, so the input is accepted. The Katydid algorithm moves high-variance input data out of memoized keys. Input objects are used only during predicate evaluation, but the memoization keys in enter and leave are alphabet independent, since they depend only on the schema argument and a boolean Vector.

3 The Katydid Algorithm

In this section, we describe the Katydid algorithm, an alphabet independent memoized filtering algorithm, defined as `Grammar.Memoize.filter`. We define its building blocks enter, leave,

`Regex.Katydid.derive`, and `Grammar.Katydid.derive`, but we start by defining *regular expressions*, which are the core of *regular hedge grammars*, our generic schema language.

3.1 Regular Expressions

A symbolic *regular expression* [5, 14, 40] is defined as an inductive type in Lean as follows:

```
inductive Regex (σ: Type) where
  | emptyset | emptystr | symbol (s: σ) | or (r1 r2: Regex σ)
  | concat (r1 r2: Regex σ) | star (r1: Regex σ) | interleave (r1 r2: Regex σ)
```

We include the `interleave` operator to handle semi-structured data, for example, unordered JSON members and XML attributes [18]. We also support the `and`, `xor`, and `complement` operators in our definitions and proofs in the [supplementary material](#), but we omit them here for brevity. We define additional operators as helper functions:

```
def onlyif (cond: Prop) [Decidable cond] (r: Regex σ): Regex σ :=
  if cond then r else emptyset
def oneOrMore (r: Regex σ) := concat r (star r)
def optional (r: Regex σ) := or r emptystr
def starAny: Regex σ := complement emptyset
def contains (r: Regex σ) := concat starAny (concat r starAny)
```

Note that `cond` is an instance of `Decidable`, which makes it possible to use it as if it were a boolean in an `if` expression’s condition. These extra operators and helper functions are used by both RELAX NG and JSON Schema, as well as in our examples and benchmarks.

3.2 Derivative of a Regular Expression

Filtering through a list of strings (which are represented as a `List (List α)`) requires validating these strings against a regular expression. This is achieved by successively taking derivatives with respect to each symbol in a string and, at the end, checking whether the resulting expression matches the empty string [5, 36]:

```
def Regex.filter (Φ: σ → α → Bool) (r: Regex σ) (xs: List (List α)) :=
  List.filter (validate Φ r) xs
def Regex.validate (Φ: σ → α → Bool) (r: Regex σ) (xs: List α): Bool :=
  null (List.foldl (derive Φ) r xs)
```

The derivative of a regular expression yields the expression that remains to be matched after consuming a list element [5, 36]:

```
def Regex.Char.derive (r: Regex Char) (a: Char): Regex Char
#guard Regex.Char.derive (concat (symbol 'a') (symbol 'b')) 'a'
  = or (concat emptystr (symbol 'b')) emptyset -- symbol 'b'
#guard Regex.Char.derive (star (symbol 'a')) 'a'
  = concat emptystr (star (symbol 'a')) -- star (symbol 'a')
```

We use Lean’s `#guard` command to show examples that are checked by the type checker. The derivative examples above can be simplified to the expressions in comments, which is common to do via smart constructors [36] when taking derivatives; however, we do not discuss this in this paper. To define the derivative of a regular hedge grammar, we need a more general version of the regular expression derivative function that is capable of supporting hedges. We achieve this by using a symbolic derivative [14, 40] over a generic input alphabet (α) and a decidable predicate (Φ):

```

def Regex.derive ( $\Phi$ :  $\sigma \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ ) (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ) (a:  $\alpha$ ): Regex  $\sigma$  :=
  match r with
  | emptyset => emptyset | emptystr => emptyset
  | symbol s => onlyif ( $\Phi$  s a) emptystr
  | or r1 r2 => or (derive  $\Phi$  r1 a) (derive  $\Phi$  r2 a)
  | concat r1 r2 => or
    (concat (derive  $\Phi$  r1 a) r2)
    (onlyif (null r1) (derive  $\Phi$  r2 a))
  | star r1 => concat (derive  $\Phi$  r1 a) (star r1)
  | interleave r1 r2 => or
    (interleave (derive  $\Phi$  r1 a) r2)
    (interleave (derive  $\Phi$  r2 a) r1)

```

theorem genderive: Regex.Char.derive r a = Regex.derive (fun s a => s == a) r a

The Lean **theorem** is used to prove that the two definitions of derive are equal when the symbol is a Char and the correctness is checked by the Lean type checker. In Regex.Char.derive, the symbol σ is of the same type as the alphabet α , but in the general case, the symbol can represent an inductive predicate type, where Φ is the evaluation function, see example in next subsection, Pred. The null function returns whether a regular expression matches the empty string [5, 14, 36]:

```

def Regex.null: (r: Regex  $\sigma$ )  $\rightarrow$  Bool
  | emptyset => false | emptystr => true | symbol _ => false
  | or r1 r2 => (null r1 || null r2) | concat r1 r2 => (null r1 && null r2)
  | star _ => true | interleave r1 r2 => (null r1 && null r2)

```

String validation can be performed by lazily constructing a DFA using memoization: the initial regular expression acts as the start state, transitions are given by the derivative function, and every distinct regular expression produced by the derivative function becomes a new state. As more strings are processed, the lazily constructed fragment of the DFA incrementally expands, allowing it to filter subsequent strings more efficiently [36]. The variance of the input parameters is small, and the number of different regular expressions is bounded by smart constructors that simplify regular expressions on construction [36].

We define Regex.Point.derive, a variation of the original Regex.derive function designed for more efficient memoization. By removing the dependency on specific list elements, it serves as a streamlined building block for the subsequent leave function to reintegrate results and take the derivative:

```

def Regex.Point.derive: (r: Regex ( $\sigma \times \text{Bool}$ ))  $\rightarrow$  Regex  $\sigma$ 
  | emptyset => emptyset | emptystr => emptyset
  | symbol (_, res) => onlyif res emptystr
  | or r1 r2 => or (derive r1) (derive r2)
  | concat r1 r2 => or
    (concat (derive r1) (first r2))
    (onlyif (null r1) (derive r2))
  | star r1 => concat (derive r1) (star (first r1))
  | interleave r1 r2 => or
    (interleave (derive r1) (first r2))
    (interleave (derive r2) (first r1))

```

Instead of the original alphabet symbols, each position now contains a tuple comprising the symbol and its predicate evaluation result ($\sigma \times \text{Bool}$). This pair can be interpreted as a point on the graph of the predicate function. In the symbol case, the result is checked, but in all other cases, the original derivative algorithm is applied by either calling `derive` or retrieving the original regular expression with the `first` function, which maps over the regular expression as a `Functor`:

```
def Regex.Point.first (r: Regex ( $\alpha \times \beta$ )): Regex  $\alpha$  := r.map (fun (s,_) => s)
```

We can prove that these two derivative functions are equivalent:

```
theorem regex_derive_is_point_derive ( $\Phi$ :  $\sigma \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ ) (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ) (a:  $\alpha$ ):
  Regex.derive  $\Phi$  r a = Regex.Point.derive (r.map (fun s => (s,  $\Phi$  s a)))
```

The proof follows from induction on `r`.

With the foundations of regular expressions in place, we now return to regular hedge grammars.

3.3 Regular Hedge Grammars

Regular hedge grammars constitute the theoretical framework most applicable to XML [18] and other serialization formats. Any XML, JSON, or Protocol Buffers data can be viewed as a *Hedge*, and schema languages such as RELAX NG, Document type definition (DTD) [50], XMLSchema [43], and JSON Schema [37] can all be translated to *regular hedge grammars* [33], barring the JSON Schema "`uniqueItems`" and "`dynamicRef`" operators, which are not regular [2, 17].

A *hedge* is an ordered list of unranked trees [8] used to model semi-structured data formats. In Lean, we define a *Hedge* inductively as follows:

```
inductive Hedge.Node ( $\alpha$ : Type) where
  | node (label:  $\alpha$ ) (children: List (Hedge.Node  $\alpha$ ))
abbrev Hedge  $\alpha$  := List (Hedge.Node  $\alpha$ )
```

We borrow our definition of *regular hedge grammars* from [33], which in turn extends the definition of regular tree grammars from [8].

Definition 3.1. A *regular hedge grammar* is a tuple $(N, T, \text{Start}, \text{Prods})$ where:

- N is a finite set of non-terminals;
- T is a finite set of terminals;
- Start is a regular expression over $T \times N$;
- Prods is a set of production rules of the form $X \rightarrow r$, where $X \in N$ and r are regular expressions over $T \times N$.

A *symbolic regular hedge grammar* is a generalization of a regular hedge grammar that is paired with a decidable predicate (Φ : $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$), where T is a finite set of symbolic predicates (φ) over a possibly infinite alphabet (α). We represent symbolic regular hedge grammars in Lean as follows:

```
structure Grammar (n: Nat) ( $\varphi$ : Type) where
  start: Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ )
  prods: Vector (Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ )) n
```

In Lean, a `Vector` has an underlying presentation of a list, but it includes a length as a parameter in the type. In the rest of this section, we justify the representation.

Non-terminals are represented as a reference `Ref n`, which is the abbreviation for the set of natural numbers smaller than `n`:

```
abbrev Ref (n: Nat) := Fin n
def lookup (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) (ref: Ref n): Regex ( $\varphi \times$  Ref n) :=
  Vector.get G.prods ref
```

The start and production rules are represented as a `Regex ($\varphi \times$ Ref n)`, which is the product of the predicate φ and the reference. The indices of the `Vector` of production rules are used for the non-terminals, which allows us to write a `lookup` function that always returns a unique rule. Our definition does not allow multiple rules per non-terminal, but this can easily be accommodated using the `Regex.or` operator.

These grammars also have useful theoretical properties. They are closed under union, intersection, and complement. Their decidable properties include satisfiability and checking whether one grammar is a subset of another, which is used for type checking [20]. Each recursion from a lookup only occurs after an evaluation of a predicate φ . This disallows arbitrary Context Free Grammars (CFGs) with undecidable properties [20].

The following is an example of a simple inductive predicate type, `Pred`, together with its corresponding decidable evaluation function `Pred.evalb`:

```
inductive Pred ( $\alpha$ : Type) where | any | eq (t:  $\alpha$ )
def Pred.evalb { $\alpha$ : Type} [DecidableEq  $\alpha$ ] (p: Pred  $\alpha$ ) (x:  $\alpha$ ): Bool :=
  match p with | Pred.eq y => x = y | Pred.any => true
```

In practice, the predicate type supports complex nested functions, including Unicode normalization, case folding, and JSON Schema "format" validations (such as email, IPv4, and dates).

The following example illustrates a regular hedge grammar:

```
def example_grammar_doc: Grammar 3 (Pred String) :=
  Grammar.mk (start := Regex.symbol (Pred.eq "doc", 0))
    (prods := #v[Regex.oneOrMore (Regex.symbol (Pred.eq "p", 1)),
      Regex.symbol (Pred.any, 2), Regex.emptystr])
```

Note, the `Vector` of production rules is constructed with the macro `#v[]`. This grammar validates the XML snippet `<doc><p><pcdata/></p><p>
</p></doc>`.

3.4 Katydid Algorithm for Regular Expressions

The `Grammar.Katydid.derive` function is defined using `Regex.Katydid.derive`, which is defined using the two memoizable functions `enter` and `leave`:

```
def Regex.Katydid.derive ( $\Phi$ :  $\sigma \rightarrow$  Bool) (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ): Regex  $\sigma$  :=
  enter r |> Vector.map  $\Phi$  |> leave r
```

This pipeline extracts the symbols of the regular expression (`enter`), evaluates the predicate at each symbol (`Vector.map Φ`), and then reintegrates the results and takes the derivative (`leave`). The `enter` function is memoized over the `Regex` parameter, whereas `leave` is memoized over the product of the `Regex` and the evaluated symbols, `Vector Bool (symcount r)`. We name the functions `enter` and `leave` to reflect that they correspond to entering and leaving a `Hedge.Node`, which we will discuss in the next subsection. Note that both of these functions are alphabet independent.

The `enter` function returns a `Vector` of the symbols contained in the regular expression:

```
def enter (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ): Vector  $\sigma$  (symcount r) := (extract r).2
#guard enter (or (symbol 'a') (star (symbol 'b'))) = #v['a', 'b']
```

The `symcount` function determines the number of symbols in a regular expression:

```
def symcount (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ): Nat
#guard symcount (or (symbol 'a') (star (symbol 'b'))) = 2
```

The symbols are extracted from the regular expression using the `extract` function. The `extract` function returns a `Vector` of symbols and a regular expression, where all the symbols have been replaced with indexes into the `Vector` from which their original symbols can be retrieved:

```
def extract (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ): Regex (Fin (symcount r))  $\times$  Vector  $\sigma$  (symcount r)
#guard extract (or (symbol 'a') (star (symbol 'b')))
= ((or (symbol 0) (star (symbol 1))), #v['a', 'b'])
```

The next step is to evaluate all the symbols by applying `Vector.map Φ` . If care is not taken, this could trigger a heap allocation in Go, which is costly in the context of this algorithm. There are several ways to avoid this heap allocation. In Go, one can pre-allocate a reusable buffer. In Lean, we define an alternative to the memoized `enter` function, `IfExpr.enter`, which returns a nested if expression over the symbols and all possible boolean `Vector` combinations. The definitions and proofs are available in the [supplementary material](#). The drawback of `IfExpr.enter` is an exponential blow-up in the space required for memoization.

The `leave` function zips the evaluated results with the original input symbols and replaces these back into the `Regex` to create a `Regex ($\sigma \times \text{Bool}$)`. Finally, `leave` applies the derivative using `Regex.Point.derive`:

```
def leave (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ) (bools: Vector Bool (symcount r)): Regex  $\sigma$  :=
  let points: Vector ( $\sigma \times \text{Bool}$ ) (symcount r) := Vector.zip (extract r).2 bools
  let rpoint: Regex ( $\sigma \times \text{Bool}$ ) := replace (extract r).1 points
  Regex.Point.derive rpoint
```

The `replace` function takes the regular expression with indexes and a `Vector` of symbols to be reinserted into the `Regex`:

```
def replace (r: Regex (Fin n)) (xs: Vector  $\sigma$  n): Regex  $\sigma$ 
#guard replace (or (symbol 0) (star (symbol 1))) #v['a', 'b']
= (or (symbol 'a') (star (symbol 'b')))
```

This implies that the `extract` and `replace` functions form an isomorphism.

```
theorem extract_replace_is_id (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ):
  r = replace (extract r).1 (extract r).2
```

More importantly, this allows us to extract all symbols, apply a function to them, and then reinsert them, which is equivalent to mapping over the `Regex` as a `Functor`, using `Regex.map`:

```
theorem extract_replace_is_map (r: Regex  $\alpha$ ) (f:  $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ ):
  Regex.map r f = replace (extract r).1 (Vector.map f (extract r).2)
```

Unfolding `enter` and `leave` yields exactly this behaviour:

```
theorem derive_unfolds_to_map ( $\Phi$ :  $\sigma \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ ) (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ) (a:  $\alpha$ ):
  Regex.Katydid.derive (flip  $\Phi$  a) r = Regex.Point.derive
    (replace (extract r).1 (Vector.map (fun s => (s,  $\Phi$  s a)) (extract r).2))
```

In this case, the mapped function `f` is `fun x => (x, Φ x a)`. With the `Regex.Katydid.derive` algorithm defined, let us move on to its role in regular hedge grammars.

3.5 Derivative of a Regular Hedge Grammar

Holstege [17] applied a derivative algorithm to JSON Schema; we refer to this as the JSONmembers algorithm. They treat the derivative of a regular hedge grammar similarly to the derivative of a regular expression, but with special handling for the symbol case:

```
def Grammar.JSONmembers.derive (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ )
  (r: Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ )) (node: Node  $\alpha$ ): Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ ) := match r with
  | Regex.symbol (pred, ref) => let <label, children> := node
    Regex.onlyif ( $\Phi$  pred label
       $\wedge$  Regex.null (List.foldl (derive G  $\Phi$ ) (G.lookup ref) children)
    ) Regex.emptystr
  ...
  termination_by (node, r)
```

Usually, Lean can automatically detect that a function will terminate, but in some cases, the termination needs to be proved via `termination_by`. Unfortunately, the JSONmembers algorithm memoizes parameters with high variance because the parameters are alphabet dependent and the JSON member alphabet has high variance. The Katydid algorithm avoids this problem by handling the symbol case within the `nodePred` predicate.

While the aim is to implement and verify a memoized variant, we first present its foundation, the non-memoized version of Katydid:

```
def Grammar.Katydid.derive (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ )
  (r: Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ )) (node: Node  $\alpha$ ): Regex ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ ) :=
  let nodePred := fun ((labelPred, ref): ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref } n$ )) =>
    let <label, children> := node
    let childr := if  $\Phi$  labelPred label then G.lookup ref else Regex.emptyset
    Regex.null (List.foldl (Grammar.Katydid.derive G  $\Phi$ ) childr children)
  Regex.Katydid.derive nodePred r -- enter r |> Vector.map nodePred |> leave r
```

If `labelPred` matches the label, we compute the derivative of the referenced regular expression and fold it over the children of the `Hedge.Node`. Notice that this folding is the same as the folding done when validating a string; see `Regex.validate`. Since regular expressions and labels are both predicates, their conjunction provides a natural mechanism for recursive Hedge validation. Also observe that `Regex.Katydid.derive` takes a partially applied predicate, where the α has already been applied. This is done to make termination obvious to the checker since `Grammar.Katydid.derive` is the function that destructs the `Hedge.Node`.

Both `Grammar.JSONmembers.derive` and `Grammar.Katydid.derive` can be used to validate a hedge against a regular hedge grammar or to filter a list of hedges:

```
def validate (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ ) (nodes: Hedge  $\alpha$ ): Bool :=
  Regex.null (List.foldl (derive G  $\Phi$ ) G.start nodes)
def filter (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ ) (hedges: List (Hedge  $\alpha$ )) :=
  List.filter (validate G  $\Phi$ ) hedges
```

3.6 Adding Memoization

To demonstrate how memoization improves the performance of derivative-based filtering over regular hedge grammars, we make the following definitions. A function is *memoizable* if its input

parameters can be hashed and have decidable equality. We express this as a Lean `class` using a Monad `m` for stateful caching:

```
class Memoize [DecidableEq  $\alpha$ ] [Hashable  $\alpha$ ] { $\beta$ :  $\alpha \rightarrow \text{Type}$ } (f: ( $a$ :  $\alpha$ )  $\rightarrow \beta$  a)
  (m:  $\text{Type} \rightarrow \text{Type}$  u) where call: ( $a$ :  $\alpha$ )  $\rightarrow m$  {  $b$ :  $\beta$  a //  $b = f$  a }
```

The return type is expressed as a Subtype, $\{ b: \beta$ a // $b = f$ a $\}$, which has a value `b` and a property that the value is equal to the output value of the original non-memoized function `f`. Other formalizations [48] additionally have an invariant that input and output values have to be stored, but the `Memoize` class allows various caching strategies, including limited space strategies.

We define memoized versions of the derivative, validate, and filter functions for both regular expressions and regular hedge grammars in the [supplementary material](#). Here is a filter type signature as an example:

```
def Grammar.Memoize.filter [DecidableEq  $\varphi$ ] [Hashable  $\varphi$ ] [Monad m]
  [MemoizeKatydid m ( $\varphi \times \text{Ref}$  n)] (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow \text{Bool}$ )
  (xs: List (Hedge  $\alpha$ )) : m { xs' // xs' = Grammar.Katydid.filter G  $\Phi$  xs }
```

We only memoize the enter and leave functions using the `MemoizeKatydid` class:

```
class MemoizeKatydid (m:  $\text{Type} \rightarrow \text{Type}$  u)  $\sigma$  [DecidableEq  $\sigma$ ] [Hashable  $\sigma$ ] where
  enterM : (r: Regex  $\sigma$ )  $\rightarrow m$  { res: Vector  $\sigma$  (symcount r) // res = enter r }
  leaveM : (param:  $\Sigma$  (r: Regex  $\sigma$ ), (Vector Bool (symcount r)))
     $\rightarrow m$  { res: Regex  $\sigma$  // res = Regex.leave param.1 param.2 }
```

We use Σ in Lean to express a dependent pair type, where the type of the second element depends on the value of the first element. This class allows one to specify a memoization strategy appropriate to the use case. We adopt a strategy that records every invocation in a State Monad.

The memoized functions are updated to use monads and to propagate soundness via the Subtype; otherwise, they are a one-to-one translation of the non-memoized functions. Propagating soundness required redefining some standard library functions (including `List.foldM`, `Vector.mapM`, and `List.filterM`) to also propagate soundness. As part of the refactoring with monads, we replace the predicate `nodePred` passed to `Regex.Katydid.derive` and give it the type $\sigma \rightarrow m \text{ Bool}$ to ensure the recursive use of memoization.

4 Verification

Verifying the correctness of our memoized filtering function, `Grammar.Memoize.filter`, requires instantiating `MemoizeKatydid` and proving that the filtered elements are exactly those that both occur in the original list and belong to the language denoted by the Grammar: $x \in \text{filter } G \text{ xs} \leftrightarrow x \in \text{xs} \wedge x \in \llbracket G \rrbracket$. The full theorem is written in Lean as:

```
theorem memoize_mem_filter [DecidableEq  $\varphi$ ] [Hashable  $\varphi$ ] (state: ...)
  (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ )  $\Phi$  [DecidableRel  $\Phi$ ] (xs: List (Hedge  $\alpha$ )):
   $\forall x$ , ( $x \in (\text{flip StateM.run}' \text{state.leave} (\text{flip StateT.run}' \text{state.enter}$ 
    ( $\text{Grammar.Memoize.filter } G (\text{decideRel } \Phi) \text{xs})))$ .val)
     $\leftrightarrow (x \in \text{xs} \wedge \text{Grammar.denote } G \Phi x)$ 
```

We instantiate `MemoizeKatydid` with a State monad and two hashtables, but the instance is not important since the proof follows by generalizing these and using the soundness that was propagated to `Grammar.Memoize.filter`.

It remains to show that the semantics of a regular hedge grammar coincide with the implementation of the `Katydid` algorithm:

```
theorem validate_commutates (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ )  $\Phi$  [DecidableRel  $\Phi$ ] (h: Hedge  $\alpha$ ):
  (validate G (decideRel  $\Phi$ ) h = true) = Grammar.denote G  $\Phi$  h
```

The `validate` function accepts a hedge if and only if it is described by the grammar, i.e. if $h \in \llbracket G \rrbracket$. To understand this theorem, we first explain how denotation defines the semantics.

4.1 Semantics

The denotation of a Regex or Grammar defines its meaning or semantics via the Language, `Lang`. The semantics of a Regex is defined as the set of strings it matches, while a Grammar is defined as the set of hedges it matches, both of which can be represented as `Lang` with a different generic parameter:

```
def Lang ( $\alpha$ : Type): Type := List  $\alpha$   $\rightarrow$  Prop
```

Whether a language matches the empty string is defined in `Lang.null`:

```
def Lang.null (R: Lang  $\alpha$ ): Prop := R []
```

The derivative of a language is the language consisting of all strings that remain after the input element has been matched:

```
def Lang.derive (R: Lang  $\alpha$ ) (x:  $\alpha$ ): Lang  $\alpha$  := fun (xs: List  $\alpha$ ) => R (x :: xs)
```

We specify the semantics of a Grammar as the denotation of the start rule:

```
def Grammar.denote (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow$  Prop) (h: Hedge  $\alpha$ ): Prop :=
  Rule.denote G  $\Phi$  G.start h
```

```
def Rule.denote (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ ) ( $\Phi$ :  $\varphi \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow$  Prop)
  (r: Regex ( $\varphi \times$  Ref n)) (h: Hedge  $\alpha$ ): Prop := match r with
| Regex.emptyset => False
| Regex.emptystr => h = []
| Regex.symbol (pred, ref) => match h with
  | [hnode] => ( $\Phi$  pred hnode.getLabel)
     $\wedge$  denote G  $\Phi$  (G.lookup ref) hnode.getChildren
| _ => False
| Regex.or r1 r2 => (denote G  $\Phi$  r1 h)  $\vee$  (denote G  $\Phi$  r2 h)
| Regex.concat r1 r2 =>  $\exists$  (i: Fin (h.length + 1)),
  (denote G  $\Phi$  r1 (List.take i h))  $\wedge$  (denote G  $\Phi$  r2 (List.drop i h))
| Regex.star r1 => match h with
  | [] => True
  | (hnode::h') =>  $\exists$  (i: Fin h.length),
    (denote G  $\Phi$  r1 (hnode::List.take i h'))
     $\wedge$  (denote G  $\Phi$  (Regex.star r1) (List.drop i h'))
| Regex.interleave r1 r2 =>  $\exists$  (i: Fin (List.interleaves h).length),
  (denote G  $\Phi$  r1 (List.get (List.interleaves h) i).1)
   $\wedge$  (denote G  $\Phi$  r2 (List.get (List.interleaves h) i).2)
termination_by (h, r)
```

We base this denotation on the denotation of regular expressions [14] and prove it to be equivalent to any alterations we made in the [supplementary material](#), except for the `symbol` and `interleave` operators, which we had to define ourselves. The `emptyset` specifies a set that contains nothing, while the `emptystr` is a singleton set containing the empty list. The `symbol` construct describes

Fig. 1. Commuting Square: $\llbracket \text{derive } r \text{ node} \rrbracket = \text{Lang.derive } \llbracket r \rrbracket \text{ node}$

only languages consisting of a single `Hedge.Node`, where the node's label satisfies the predicate `pred` and its children belong to the referenced language. The `or` expression denotes the union of two languages, whereas the `concat` expression contains a `Hedge` only if it can be decomposed into a prefix and a suffix, such that the prefix belongs to the first language and the suffix belongs to the second. The `star` expression includes the empty list and any combination of a prefix from the underlying expression `r1` followed by any number of its repetitions. The `interleave` of two languages only matches if the two languages match one of the possible interleaves of the `Hedge`:

```
def interleaves (xs: List α) (acc: List (List α × List α) := [([], [])])
  : List (List α × List α) := match xs with
  | [] => acc
  | (x::xs) => (interleaves xs acc).map (fun res => (x::res.1, res.2))
              ++ (interleaves xs acc).map (fun res => (res.1, x::res.2))
#guard (interleaves [1,2,3,4]).contains ([1,3],[2,4])
```

We use this definition to avoid termination issues and prove it equivalent to an alternative definition [7], in the [supplementary material](#), to regain confidence.

Verifying the correctness of this denotation is simplified by observing that the `Rule.denote` function coincides with the denotation of a `Regex` in all cases except `symbol`:

```
def Regex.denote (Φ: σ → α → Prop) (r: Regex σ) (xs: List α): Prop :=
  match r with
  | symbol s => match xs with
  | [x] => Φ s x | _ => False
  ...
```

We further observe that the only difference between the two `symbol` cases is that $\Phi \ s \ x$ is replaced by $\Phi \ \text{pred} \ \text{node.getLabel} \ \backslash \ \text{denote } G \ \Phi \ (G.\text{lookup } \text{ref}) \ \text{node.getChildren}$. This renders `Regex.denote` and `Rule.denote` analogous, as both amount to checking a predicate over a list containing a single element.

4.2 The Proof

The proof of `theorem validate_commutes` requires two theorems. The first theorem states that the denotation of a `Grammar` matching the empty list is equivalent to the definition of `Regex.null`:

```
theorem null_commutes (G: Grammar n φ) (Φ: φ → α → Prop) [DecidableRel Φ] r:
  ((Regex.null r) = true) = Lang.null (Rule.denote G Φ r)
```

This proof follows from induction on the regular expression `r`.

The second theorem states that the derivative algorithm satisfies the commuting square shown in Figure 1:

```
theorem derive_commutates (G: Grammar n  $\varphi$ )  $\Phi$  [DecidableRel  $\Phi$ ]
  (r: Regex ( $\varphi \times$  Ref n)) (node: Node  $\alpha$ ):
  Rule.denote G  $\Phi$  (derive G (decideRel  $\Phi$ ) r node)
  = Lang.derive (Rule.denote G  $\Phi$  r) node
```

Note that we use `decideRel` to convert a decidable relation that returns a property to a decidable predicate that returns a boolean:

```
def decideRel (p :  $\alpha \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow$  Prop) [DecidableRel p]:  $\alpha \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow$  Bool :=
  fun a b => decide (p a b)
```

We prove that the derivative and denotation squares commute for both the JSONmembers and Katydid algorithms, which implies that validation and filtering proofs follow for each algorithm, including the memoized Katydid algorithm, `theorem memoize_mem_filter`.

We first verify `theorem derive_commutates` for `Grammar.JSONmembers.derive`. The proof begins with functional induction on `Grammar.JSONmembers.derive`, producing an inductive hypothesis applicable to the symbol case. All cases are trivial except for the symbol case, where we additionally perform induction on the children and apply the functional inductive hypothesis.

Next, we prove `theorem derive_commutates` for `Grammar.Katydid.derive`. For each operator except `symbol`, we complete the proof by induction on the regular expression, undoing the partial application of `node`, permuting the parameters, and applying `theorem Regex.Katydid.derive_is_Regex_derive`, which establishes the equivalence of `Regex.Katydid.derive` and `Regex.derive`:

```
theorem Regex.Katydid.derive_is_Regex_derive ( $\Phi$ :  $\sigma \rightarrow \alpha \rightarrow$  Bool) r a:
  Regex.Katydid.derive (flip  $\Phi$  a) r = Regex.derive  $\Phi$  r a
```

This is proven by `theorem extract_replace_is_map` and `theorem regex_derive_is_point_derive`.

We also need to perform two inductions for the symbol case, one for the Grammar and one for the Hedge, as in the proof of `theorem derive_commutates` for `Grammar.JSONmembers.derive`. Unlike the JSONmembers algorithm's proof, we cannot apply functional induction to a recursive closure and therefore lack an inductive hypothesis in the symbol case. The proof proceeds by applying induction on the children, followed by using well-founded induction with recursive calls to `theorem derive_commutates`.

4.3 Reflections on the Proof

The proof relies on two key observations: first, that the algorithm for regular hedge grammars can be generalized to regular expressions via a recursive predicate closure; and second, that the algorithm as a whole amounts to a map operation, up to the final derivative step.

The remainder of the proof is complicated by termination arguments. We avoided a termination proof for `Grammar.Katydid.derive` by partially applying the `Hedge.Node` parameter, but termination proofs were required for `Rule.denote` in the `star` case and `theorem derive_commutates` for `Grammar.Katydid.derive` in the symbol case. In `Rule.denote` we needed to use a `match` expression instead of an \exists operator for termination proof purposes, where \exists would have been more appropriate for a denotation function.

Handling the recursive closure required extensive iterations over possible termination arguments, unfoldings, and simplifications. We attempted several versions of the proof to properly unfold, simplify, and prove the termination of the recursive closure. The most intricate part was the

termination proof of `theorem derive_commutates` for `Grammar.Katydid.derive`, which relied on the size of the `Hedge.Node` decreasing. We had to redeclare the well-founded induction call using a membership relation: `fun r' x (hx: x ∈ children) => derive_commutates G Φ r' x`. This gave us the hypothesis we needed to prove termination. We encountered a similar termination issue when propagating memoization soundness, which required redefining `List.foldM` to both propagate soundness and track that each child is an element of the children list.

4.4 Compiling the Memoization Table

All entries in the memoization tables of `enter` and `leave` can be precomputed without any input:

```
def Regex.compile [DecidableEq σ] [Hashable σ] [Monad m] [MemoizeKatydid m σ]
  (r: Regex σ): m Unit := do
  for r in Regex.derivatives r do
    _ ← MemoizeKatydid.enterM r
    for bools in Vector.boolCombos (symcount r) do
      _ ← MemoizeKatydid.leaveM ⟨r, bools⟩
```

`Regex.derivatives` calculates a list of all dissimilar derivatives of a regular expression. We have not formally verified that this list is finite, but it has been proven for regular expressions by Brzozowski [5], formally verified by Zhuchko et al. [51], and proven for the interleave operator [41]. In the case of `leave`, we also have to calculate the extra input parameter for all boolean combinations; see `Vector.boolCombos`. Lean’s notation for Monads (`do`, `←`) updates the memoization tables and includes support for imperative `for` loops. The fact that the memoization table, as computed by `Regex.compile`, has a bounded size is verified by Lean’s termination checker. We extend this compilation to the whole grammar by calling `Regex.compile` for each of the finite list of production rules to complete the fully precomputed memoization table. As a result, the combined number of entries in the `enter` and `leave` memoization tables is at most $\sum_{r \in R} |\Delta_r| + 2^{\maxs(\Delta_r)}$, where R is $G.\text{prods} \cup \{G.\text{start}\}$, Δ_r is the list `Regex.derivatives r`, and $\maxs(\Delta_r)$ denotes the maximum `symcount` over $r' \in \Delta_r$.

5 Go Implementation

The `Katydid` algorithm was originally implemented in Go, back in 2016, to filter through petabytes of serialized Protocol Buffers in a proprietary distributed database. The Go implementation includes optimizations for faster validation beyond the verified memoization technique. The optimization that is considered a major contribution is the fusion of the derivative and parsing algorithms. Other simple optimizations beyond the scope of this paper include smart constructors that simplify regular expressions and compute nullability and hashes for comparisons. In the previous section, we verified `Katydid`’s memoization technique for regular hedge grammars. To be precise about the scope: the `enter/leave` memoization technique and its correctness are verified in Lean (Section 4), whereas the fused algorithm, the JSON Schema-to-grammar translation, and the other simple optimizations are implemented in Go, but not yet verified in Lean. In this section, we continue to use Lean as pseudocode to explain the rest of the Go implementation. We start by explaining the pull-based parser, which is required for fusion.

5.1 Pull-Based Parser

We designed a pull-based parser interface to be lazy enough to parse only what is required and generic enough to handle any sequential serialized data format. A pull-based parser avoids the need to create an intermediate parsing data structure, in our case a `Hedge`, which enables our

fused derivative algorithm in [Section 5.2](#). A pull-based parser operates like an event-based parser, for example, a Simple API for XML (SAX) [4] parser, but instead of pushing events to a callback function, it requires methods to be called for parsing to progress:

```
class Parser (m: Type → Type u) (α: outParam Type) where
  next: m Hint
  token: m α
  skip: m Unit
```

The α type parameter will be the values returned by our parser, while the m type parameter will be a Monad, which, in our implementations, means the methods can return errors and the parser has some state in the form of a stack. When the `next` method is called, the implementation parses what is required and returns only a hint of whether we are entering or leaving a structure or have reached a value:

```
inductive Hint where | enter | leave | value | eof
```

To avoid unnecessary parsing, the value, such as a 64-bit integer, is only parsed when the `token` method is called. Our Parser implementations are all of type `Parser Token`, which means the `token` method returns a `Token`:

```
inductive Token where
  | null | bool (v: Bool) | string (v: String) | bytes (v: Bytes)
  | int64 (v: Int64) | float64 (v: Float64Bits) | decimal (v: String)
  | nanoseconds (v: Int64) | datetime (v: String) | tag (v: String)
deriving DecidableEq, Ord, Repr, Hashable
```

We base our set of token kinds on a survey of serialization formats conducted by Viotti and Kinderkhedha [46]. We also introduce a `skip` method to avoid the parsing of children. Skipping is efficient in the case of Protocol Buffers, because of the length-delimited encoding.

Consider the following Hedge representation of the JSON example discussed earlier:

```
#guard runs exampleParse [
  node (Token.string "author") [
    node (Token.string "username") [node (Token.string "Khaleesi") []]],
  node (Token.string "content") []]
```

We can parse it using an implementation of our Parser for Hedges:

```
def exampleParse [p: Parser m Token] ...: m Unit := do
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.enter -- enter blogpost
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.value; assertEq (← p.token) (string "author")
  _ ← p.skip -- skip author's children, username, ...
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.value; assertEq (← p.token) (string "content")
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.enter; assertEq (← p.next) Hint.leave
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.leave -- leave blogpost
  assertEq (← p.next) Hint.eof
```

We built pull-based parsers for JSON and Protocol Buffers that are optimized to avoid any allocation on the heap. We also built a pull-based parser for already parsed structures using Go's `reflect` library. This allows us to emulate an unfused version of the algorithm for benchmarking purposes. Unfortunately, this parser and the unoptimized XML parser make many heap allocations.

5.2 Fused Katydid Algorithm

We create an algorithm that fuses [16] the derivative and parsing algorithms to avoid creating an intermediate Hedge data structure, which avoids unnecessary allocations and copying. This fused algorithm requires a FusedKatydid class that extends both the MemoizeKatydid and Parser classes:

```
class FusedKatydid (m: Type → Type u) (σ: Type) (α: Type)
  [DecidableEq σ] [Hashable σ] extends
  Monad m, MonadExcept String m, Parser m α, MemoizeKatydid m σ
```

We created an alternative to the MemoizeKatydid class called MemoizeKatydid that handles Vectors of regular expressions instead of single regular expressions. This was necessary since the fused algorithm uses the Parser, which is an online parser and therefore performs no backtracking, requiring the order of Hedge traversal to be refactored:

```
partial def Grammar.Fused.derive
  [DecidableEq φ] [Hashable φ] [FusedKatydid m (φ × Ref n) α]
  (G: Grammar n φ) (Φ: φ → m α → m Bool)
  (rs: Vector (Regex (φ × Ref n)) l): m (Vector (Regex (φ × Ref n)) l) := do
  let mut drs := rs
  if Vector.all rs Regex.unescapable then Parser.skip; return drs
  let mut h := ← Parser.next
  while h == Hint.value do
    let enterSymbols ← MemoizeKatydid.entersM ⟨l, drs⟩
    let childrs ← Vector.mapM (xs := enterSymbols.val) (fun ⟨pred, ref⟩ => do
      return if ← Φ pred Parser.token then G.lookup ref else emptyset)
    let childbs ← Vector.mapM Regex.null <$> Fused.derive G Φ childrs
    drs := ← MemoizeKatydid.leavesM ⟨l, drs, childbs⟩
    h := ← Parser.next
  if h == Hint.enter then Fused.derive G Φ rs else return drs
```

We start each call to fusedDerive with a check to determine whether we can skip parsing the children since the Vector rs could be empty or could only contain emptyset elements. We then check if the Hint is a value or enter, in which case we can either loop through all the values or recurse until a leave Hint is received. Handling this new traversal order requires the memoized functions (enterM and leaveM) to be adjusted to operate on a Vector of Regex rather than on a single Regex. The newly adjusted functions entersM and leavesM require the length of the Vector to also be memoized; hence, the addition of l in their dependent pair parameters, which is constructed using ⟨⟩. We use Lean's notation for Monads (do, ←, ;, <\$>) to check for errors, handle the mutation of the parser state and memoization table, implement an imperative loop (while), do control flow via an early return, and handle mutable variables (mut, :=). Notice that the predicate evaluation function Φ is responsible for calling the token method so that it is only done if it is truly necessary. We define fusedDerive using partial since we have not proven that it terminates.

There are other optimizations not included here. Evaluating the predicates can be expensive, but we optimize many string equalities with various hash map strategies. The Vector childrs is also compressed before calling fusedDerive. This is done by removing duplicates, emptyset, and starAny. The resulting Vector childbs is then decompressed to match the original length of childrs using a Vector of indices that the compression function emitted.

5.3 Supporting JSON Schema

Holstege [17] explains how JSON Schema can be converted to *tagged-type regular expressions*. They support additional operators, including `interleave`, `xor` and `ifthenelse`. They show that translation is possible, except for non-regular operators such as `"uniqueItems"` and `"$dynamicRef"`. Unlike `"uniqueItems"`, `"$dynamicRef"` is still an unpopular feature. After analyzing 31,000 schemas, Viotti and Mior [47] found only 10 uses of `"$dynamicRef"` on GitHub.

We benchmark our algorithm against other JSON Schema libraries. To achieve this, we implement our own translation algorithm from JSON Schema to regular hedge grammars. To illustrate our translation, consider the following trivial example of how the JSON is parsed. The JSON `{"a": ["b", "c"]}` is represented as the following Hedge, abstracted away behind a performant, pull-based parser:

```
[node (tag "object") [node (string "a") [node (tag "array") [
  node (int64 0) [node (string "b") []],
  node (int64 1) [node (string "c") []]]]]]
```

The objects and arrays are tagged with labels to help us support JSON Schema's `{"type": "object"}` and `{"type": "array"}`. The arrays are indexed, which makes them behave similarly to objects with field names. Finally, the Hedge is parameterized over the Token type.

We can translate the `"small jsonschema for a blogpost"` example into a regular hedge grammar:

```
def example_translated_jsonschema : Grammar 7 Pred := Grammar.mk
  (start := (symbol (tagEq "object", 4)))
  (prods := #v[emptystr, starAny, symbol (string, 0), symbol (email, 0)
    , (interleave (symbol (strEq "content", 2))
      (optional (symbol (strEq "author", 5))))
    , (symbol (tagEq "object", 6))
    , (interleave (symbol (strEq "username", 2))
      (optional (symbol (strEq "email", 3))))])
```

Most operators translate seamlessly, such as `"anyOf"`, `"allOf"`, `"oneOf"`, and `"not"`. Others posed a challenge: `"dependentRequired"`, `"patternProperties"` and `"additionalProperties"`. For example, if the `"additionalProperties"` field is not set, it defaults to true, which means other fields are allowed. Therefore, we need to add an extra constraint that matches any fields that were not already defined:

```
star (symbol (not (or (strEq "content") (strEq "author"))), 1))
```

We evaluated our translation against the JSON Schema Draft4 test suite. Out of 924 total test cases, our implementation successfully passed 838. The failures were strictly isolated to test cases involving the unsupported features: `"remoteRef"` and `"uniqueItems"`. We also tested whether our translation found all valid and invalid instances of the benchmarks, respectively valid and invalid. We leave it as future work to support more versions of JSON Schema.

6 Benchmarks

We conduct benchmarks to show that Brzozowski [5] derivatives are not only convenient for correctness guarantees, but can also be competitive for the validation of semi-structured data. The benchmarks are completed on variations of the Katydid algorithm in Go. We include two variations of the Katydid algorithm: *Memo* and *Comp*. The *Memo* version of the algorithm memoizes as the

Fig. 2. Memoization Benchmarks

regular hedge grammar is exercised. The *Comp* version compiles the regular hedge grammar by prepopulating the memoization tables with all possibilities. We also include various implementations of the pull-based parser: JSON, Proto (Protocol Buffer), and a Go reflection-based parser that first deserializes into a Go structure and then parses that structure using Go's reflect library. All benchmarks were run on a 2024 MacBook Pro M4 with 48 GB of memory.

6.1 Memoization Benchmarks

We start by benchmarking how memoization increases efficiency over time using the JSON and Proto implementations of the Parser. Two regular hedge grammars (simple and complex) were chosen to filter a list of conferences:

```
def simple: Grammar 2 (Pred String) :=
  mk (field ("Category", 1)) #v[emptystr, eq ("Computer Science", 0)]
def complex: Grammar 7 (Pred String) :=
  mk (interleave (eq ("Due", 1)) (interleave (eq ("Loc", 5)) starAny))
  #v[emptystr,
    or (field ("Year", 2)) (and (field ("Year", 3)) (field ("Month", 4))),
    eq ("2026", 0), eq ("2025", 0), symbol (Pred.ge "10", 0),
    field ("Cont", 6), eq ("EU", 0)]
def eq (v:  $\alpha \times \text{Fin } n$ ) := symbol (Pred.eq v.1, v.2)
def field (v:  $\alpha \times \text{Fin } n$ ) := contains (symbol (Pred.eq v.1, v.2))
```

The simple grammar filters for conferences within the Category of Computer Science, while the complex grammar filters for conferences that have submission deadlines in 2026 or after October 2025 and are also located on the continent of Europe. For each grammar, we randomly populated data structures and serialized them as Protocol Buffers and JSON.

Note that we also ran benchmarks back in 2016 and achieved similar sub-microsecond results for similar grammars on older hardware. We conducted benchmarks over several iterations to evaluate how memoization improves filter efficiency with repeated execution. The [supplementary material](#) includes a more extensive benchmark suite, recorded runs, and explains how to reproduce the benchmarks.

The results of the benchmarks are shown in [Figure 2](#). We ran each grammar for multiple iterations. We recorded the mean running time while memoizing for the number of iterations specified after

Memo, where Comp is compiled, and *NoMemo* has no memoization table. We observe that the longer the same grammar is memoized, the faster the algorithm becomes. Once the functions are fully memoized over all possible cases, the benchmarks indicate zero heap allocations. Notice that the JSON benchmarks are slower than the Proto benchmarks for the same complex grammar. This shift occurs because Protocol Buffers offer superior parsing speeds; our profiling confirms that parsing has become the primary CPU bottleneck.

6.2 JSON Schema Benchmarks

We chose JSON Schema to conduct benchmarks against other validators, since it is a schema language with a close relationship to regular hedge grammars and has many implementations to benchmark against. Viotti and Mior [47] developed a benchmark suite for JSON Schema. They collected schemas from the JSON Schema Store [23] and then crawled GitHub for valid JSON documents for each of these schemas. We significantly extended this benchmark suite by adding:

- Measurement of parse times;
- Schemas from JSON Schema examples [21], Ajv's [38] benchmarks, and the conference example previously introduced, resulting in a total of 45 unique schemas; see a summary in the [supplementary material](#);
- Random generation of valid and invalid JSON Schema documents for these new schemas;
- A mutator to mutate the valid instances collected by Viotti and Mior [47] into invalid instances;
- Correctness of the benchmark implementations by checking that they not only accept valid schemas but also reject invalid schemas, which resulted in the reporting of several bugs and updating them with their fixes;
- Support for JSON Schema "*format*" in all implementations.

We also extend the benchmark suite of [47] with use cases that include parse times and invalid documents, for a total of three use cases: (1) Filtering: simulating a user searching through a large database for a few records. We benchmark against only invalid documents and include parsing time. (2) API Gateway (reuse): validates documents for security purposes, where mostly valid documents are expected. We benchmark against only valid documents and exclude parsing time. (3) API Gateway (discard): The same as API Gateway (reuse), but we include parsing time. We extended the suite with a separate measurement of JSON parsing time, allowing us to benchmark the effective cost of validation depending on whether the parsed JSON is reused for later processing or discarded after validation; see the API Gateway (discard) use case. This is also important when analyzing validators filtering large volumes of documents since most documents will not match and will be discarded; see the Filtering use case. Therefore, the benchmark should include the parsing time overhead, which is an integral component of total validation time. Other cases where the parsed document is discarded include: (1) Validation is performed by a separate API gateway service, and downstream services must parse the JSON again; (2) The consumer of the validation output expects the JSON to be deserialized into user-defined, statically typed data structures, which have specified field names, as they are faster and safer to use than a hash map; (3) The validation library's implementation language is different from the target language of the consumer. In some cases, copying or translating the validator's parsed JSON representation may not require reparsing. However, we use parsing time as an approximation of this additional cost since we expect that most users would rather reparse the JSON in these scenarios.

We benchmark the compiled Katydid version against 18 other implementations in various programming languages. In the API Gateway (reuse) benchmarks, we use the unfused version of Katydid with the reflection-based parser since this is the only way that reuse is possible. Each

Table 2. Filtering

#	impl	language	median ns/doc	mean ns/doc
1	Katydid	Golang	1,361	9,568
2	Ajv-Bun	Javascript (gen)	1,928	6,970
3	Blaze	C++	2,645	12,729
4	JSU	Javascript (gen)	2,728	10,341
5	networknt	Java	3,000	32,474
6	boon	Rust	3,173	36,697
7	JSU	Python (gen)	3,336	25,231
8	Ajv	Javascript (gen)	3,572	12,629
9	JSU	C++ (gen)	4,139	25,724
10	santhosh-tekuri	Golang	7,993	78,244
11	OptimumCode	Kotlin	10,232	132,604
12	JSU	Java (gen)	10,310	30,663
13	JSV	Elixir	11,732	369,538
14	Corvus	C# (gen)	12,813	42,210
15	kaptinlin	Golang	18,551	267,674
16	json-everything	C#	28,390	695,042
17	py-jsonschema	Python	29,846	1,446,531
18	JSONSchemer	Ruby	41,906	728,676
19	Hyperjump	Javascript	212,527	621,062

Table 3. API Gateway (reuse)

#	impl	language	median ns/doc	mean ns/doc
1	JSU	C++ (gen)	136	1,397
2	Blaze	C++	148	1,187
4	Ajv	Javascript (Bun)	329	2,836
11	Katydid	Golang	1,691	18,289
13	santhosh-tekuri	Golang	2,889	50,588
15	kaptinlin	Golang	12,466	247,007
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

This is an excerpt of full table in [supplementary material](#), where the # column denotes median rank

implementation is warmed up by first validating all the documents for over a hundred iterations. This implies that the CPU caches are warmed up, the JIT has been triggered, and that our memoized solution has a populated table. This is representative of real-world situations of an API gateway or filtering through petabytes of records. For each schema, we measure the mean run time over all its instances. To ensure statistical stability, we calculate the mean of three separate runs. For each implementation, we then report the median and mean across all schemas. Details of how implementations were chosen and additional measurements, such as memory usage, can be found in the [supplementary material](#).

We see in [Table 2](#) that Katydid has the fastest median latency and the second fastest mean for the filtering use case. Katydid is the fastest for 35 out of the 45 schemas, while Ajv on the Javascript Bun runtime (Ajv-Bun) is the fastest for 9 other schemas, and JSU (Javascript) is the fastest for one. The mean is skewed towards Ajv-Bun because there are three schemas where the winning time is an order of magnitude larger than for the other schemas, and two more are two orders larger. The slowest schema, geojson, is where Katydid is 2-3 times slower than Ajv-Bun. We do not exactly know how Ajv-Bun achieves this speed; maybe it is the code generation or the way the BUN runtime parses JSON, but we note that Katydid is still faster in this case than Blaze, an optimized C++ implementation. In the API Gateway (discard) use case, which we include in the [supplementary material](#), Katydid also has the fastest median but the third fastest mean, with Ajv-Bun having the fastest mean again. In this use case, Ajv-Bun is the fastest for 22 out of the 45 schemas, and Katydid is the fastest for 21 others. Finally, we find that even though Katydid is not the fastest library for the API gateway (reuse) use case, it is still competitive and the fastest Go library; see [Table 3](#).

Threats to the validity of benchmarking results include:

- Katydid, Ajv, Blaze, JSONSchemer, JSU, OptimumCode, networknt, py-jsonschema return booleans and not detailed errors. In the filtering case, this gives them an advantage by not allocating memory over implementations that create descriptions of validation errors.
- When Blaze parses JSON, it also calculates hashes for field names, which allows it to perform faster string comparisons. One could argue that this is part of the validation calculation happening at parse time, and we should always add parse time to validation time. One could also argue that this is just a custom implementation of a hash map and a perfectly generic dictionary, which would be reused.
- JSU, AJV and Corvus generate code in the target language, which is a big advantage for inlining many instructions. On the other hand, Viotti and Mior [47] found from their analysis on GitHub that schemas only change on average every 61 days, so it is perfectly reasonable to generate code and precompile the schema in the API Gateway use cases, but this might not be viable for filtering.
- The Regular expression library chosen by each implementation to handle JSON Schema patterns can make a big difference. We know that at least Blaze and Katydid attempt a fast path for simple regular expressions like prefix, suffix, and character sets.
- The implementation language also skews results; see, for example, the big difference in performance between various versions of JSU.
- Very large schemas required the Comp version of Katydid to fall back to the Memo version since the Vector of booleans that needed to be calculated for the leave table was larger than twenty, which would require calculating more than a million combinations. There is work to be done to eliminate the impossible cases since many of the predicates are disjoint. The fallback rarely happens, though, as it was only triggered by two of the benchmark schemas and none of the test suite cases.

A use case we did not benchmark is deserializing directly into the user-defined data structure and then validating this structure. As far as we know, this is only supported by Katydid and kaptinlin [22], but it provides a major advantage in the API Gateway use case since, with this functionality, the user only needs to parse the JSON once, and no copies occur between generic and user-defined structures. Katydid achieves this by implementing a reflection-based pull-based parser, which demonstrates its significant flexibility.

7 Related Work

Derivatives of regular expressions have previously been formalized in proof assistants such as Agda [14], Lean [52], Isabelle/HOL [34], Idris [28] and Coq [6, 9, 11, 13, 30, 35]. To the best of our knowledge, no comparable formalization exists for schema languages or regular hedge grammars based on derivatives.

The RapidJSON [42] JSON Schema validator uses a SAX like event-based parser for JSON, which stops parsing as soon as the document is found to be invalid according to the schema. We did not include it in the benchmarks since it lacks support for JSON Schema "format", which are represented in most of the schemas in the benchmark suite. Blaze [47], like most of the other JSON Schema validators we used in our benchmarks, parses the whole JSON structure before trying to validate the document. Blaze compiles JSON Schema to its own internal Domain Specific Language (DSL) that it optimizes by reordering instructions, unrolling loops, and specialized hashing. They found that 95% of field names in their data set are shorter than 14 characters, so they created a perfect hashing function for strings consisting of 31 bytes or fewer. This makes the comparison of common string cases very fast via four 64-bit integers. These hashes are stored in a custom JSON Object into which the JSON is parsed before validation. This implies that some validation preprocessing happens during parse time.

We found our original inspiration for using derivatives to filter semi-structured data from RELAX NG [7], which converts their regular hedge grammar to a BCFG on the fly while taking the derivative. A BCFG is a CFG where every production rule is enclosed by matching terminals. These terminals function like XML opening and closing tags, ensuring that each rule is explicitly delimited. This avoids the left-recursion issues that arise when applying derivatives to CFGs [29] and enables the use of a simple derivative algorithm based on regular expressions with reference lookups. RELAX NG also includes additional operators, such as *interleave*, to model semi-structured XML content, in particular, the unordered nature of attributes. They also rely on memoization for efficiency by decomposing the derivative function into multiple smaller functions: `startTagOpenDeriv`, `attsDeriv`, `startTagCloseDeriv`, `endTagDeriv`, and `textDeriv`. Except for `textDeriv`, all functions are memoized; memoizing `textDeriv` is impractical due to the large and highly variable text-node alphabet. This shortcoming is avoided by the Katydid algorithm, which never relies on the input alphabet for memoization, while still remaining applicable to leaf nodes. The remaining memoized functions operate on element tags and attribute names, which may come from large alphabets but whose actual values exhibit low variability. An on-the-fly conversion from a regular hedge grammar to a BCFG incurs the overhead of introducing closing tags to ensure grammatical balance, which RELAX NG implements with its `after` expression. For example, consider the grammar `Grammar.mk (symbol "<div>", 0) #v[optional (symbol "<div>", 0)]` and the input string `<div><div><div></div></div></div>`. Each invocation of `startTagOpenDeriv` on a `<div>` produces a progressively larger expression that accumulates closing tags:

```
after (g.lookup 0) emptystr -- <div><div></div></div></div>
after (g.lookup 0) (after emptystr emptystr) -- <div></div></div></div>
after (g.lookup 0) (after emptystr (after emptystr emptystr))
```

This makes it impossible to always build a fully memoized version of the functions up front, since the state space is technically unbounded. In practice, recursion depths are shallow, so after validating a few documents, memoization tables are hit frequently, whereas Katydid's memoization tables are hit after the first recursive step. Another drawback is that the expression keeps more context than is necessary. For example, consider the grammar:

```
Grammar.mk (concat (symbol ("<head>", 0)) (symbol ("<body>", 0)))
  #v[optional (symbol ("<div>", 0))]
```

Applying `startTagOpenDeriv` to `<head>` yields after `(optional (symbol ("<div>", 0))) (symbol ("<body>", 0))`, which still retains the `<body>` symbol. In contrast, `Katydid` propagates only `optional (symbol ("<div>", 0))` to the children, leading to more frequent memoization table hits. Overall, RELAX NG provides an elegant and efficient approach to XML validation, albeit theoretically slightly less efficient than the `Katydid` algorithm.

Derivative-based validation is not the only automata-theoretic route to schema validation. The semantics, complexity, and expressive power of JSON Schema have been formalized [37] to find that most operators are expressible using tree automata, except for non-regular operators, such as the `"uniqueItems"` operator, which could be used to specify perfectly balanced binary trees. A classical alternative is to compile the schema to element automata or hedge/tree automata and validate by running the compiled machine over the document. In the XML setting, Murata et al. [33] gives depth-first validation algorithms for regular tree grammars based on compiled automata and shows that these scans are linear in document size for fixed schemas while being implementable over either tree-based or event-based APIs. More specifically, Hosoya and Murata [19] presented a validation algorithm that utilizes attribute-element automata that explicitly incorporate both element and attribute transitions. From a complexity perspective, this approach by Hosoya and Murata [19] offers a linear-time membership for deterministic compiled automata, polynomial-time uniform membership in the automaton-as-input setting, and good compatibility with event-driven XML parsing. Its main trade-off against derivatives is that it shifts work toward compilation, determinization, and automaton manipulation, whereas derivatives keep the runtime representation closer to the source schema and can exploit laziness and memoization on the actually visited part of the state space.

Visibly Pushdown Automata (VPA) [1] were also considered, as they have been used successfully for complex XML processing [32] as well as for fast filtering [24]. These automata include a stack and a call and return function, which we could apply to regular hedge grammars. We can construct a VPA lazily by memoizing derivatives. These memoization tables would also be larger and result in fewer hits because of the large input alphabet and variance in the labels of the text nodes, similar to RELAX NG, but the state space would be bounded.

Derivatives have been applied to JSON Schema [17] validation using an algorithm similar to `Grammar.JSONmembers.derive`. They convert JSON Schema to a grammar similar to a regular hedge grammar extended with additional operators, including `interleave`, `xor` and `ifthenelse`. The `"uniqueItems"` operator of JSON Schema is not supported since it is not regular. They test different caching approaches, but with the large Hedge .Node alphabet, they identify the approach as unpromising. Ultimately, they do achieve filtering of tens of thousands of records per second. They note that some optimizations would be possible if derivative rules took into account the unique field name constraint of JSON objects.

Several validation languages have been proposed for Protocol Buffers and Thrift [39]. Their structure is already specified using an Interface Definition Language (IDL), which serves as a schema for generating code in target programming languages but provides only limited constraints on field values beyond basic data types. Several validation languages have emerged, including ProtoML [25], which translates Protocol Buffers into a Document Object Model (DOM) and applies predicates via XPath [12]. Other examples include Scrooge Thrift Validation [44] and go-proto-validators [49], which support validation through annotations directly on the IDL. Unlike ProtoML, these tools are limited to validation and are not built for filtering, since the original IDL permits only a single field-validation specification, making the definition of multiple distinct filters impractical. The

combination of field-value validation and structural validation is strictly less expressive than regular hedge grammars and can therefore be subsumed by the Katydid algorithm. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, these validators first deserialize the input structure prior to validation, leading to unnecessary heap allocations when validation fails. Although pragmatic and user-friendly, there is room for more efficiency considerations.

8 Conclusions

We provided a fused-memoized derivative-based Katydid algorithm for the validation of semi-structured data. We chose a generic representation of serialization formats and schema languages, a Hedge and a symbolic regular hedge grammar, which makes our algorithm and verification approach applicable to any schema language and data format that can be translated into this representation. Our algorithm is fast, especially for filtering, since it avoids creating intermediate parsing data structures. We benchmarked against JSON Schema implementations and found that Katydid has the lowest median time for filtering and is competitive for API gateway validation. This demonstrates that a derivative approach can be competitive with other semi-structured validation implementations. As far as we know, ours is the first verification in an interactive theorem prover of an algorithm for the validation of semi-structured data against a regular hedge grammar.

8.1 Future Work

In the future, benchmarking could be extended to include other validation languages, implementation languages, features, and parsing could be further optimized. For example, implementing a JSON pull-based parser and JSON Schema translator in Lean would open up the possibility of benchmarking and validating the Go implementation against the Lean implementation via differential testing. Our pull-based JSON parser could be further optimized using SIMD, a faster way of parsing JSON using specialized CPU instructions [26]. Other languages to benchmark against include RELAX NG for XML validation. Regular expression matchers have been extended with non-regular features while keeping much of the matching machinery—for example, backreferences [3]. Non-regular extensions could be considered for Katydid and regular hedge grammars as well: JSON Schema’s “`uniqueItems`” is not regular [17, 37], and validating “`$dynamicRef`” is PSPACE-complete [2].

There are ample opportunities for future work in terms of correctness. It is still open to prove the correctness of the conversion algorithms from JSON Schema [17] and RELAX NG to regular hedge grammars, ensuring fully verified validators of schema languages. We also plan to prove the correctness of optimizations used in the Go implementation, including the pull-based parser and our fused algorithm. Together, these avenues move toward fully verified, high-throughput validators for semi-structured data formats that pervade modern data systems.

Supplementary Material

Full proofs in Lean, Go implementation, and benchmarks are available:

- Lean Verification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109287>;
- JSON Schema benchmarks: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109315>;
- Go JSON Schema implementation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109322>;
- Memoization benchmarks runner: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109312>; and
- Memoization benchmark suite <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109306>.

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